

Incipient Bearing Fault Signature Identification via Vibration Envelope Analysis and MUSIC

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Abstract—Rolling bearings represent the weakest element in low-voltage machines from a maintenance perspective. The detection of localized bearing faults in steady-state conditions is widely studied via vibration envelope analysis. However, the detection of these faults during the machine start-up presents increased challenges such as the accurate monitoring of time-evolving components. This paper introduces a time-frequency analysis tool to qualitatively evaluate localized bearing faults evolutions during an inverter-fed machine start-up. Transient vibration signal envelope is translated into the time-frequency domain by utilizing the Multiple Signal Classification (MUSIC) pseudo-spectrum. Furthermore, a thorough sensitivity analysis is performed to elucidate the strengths and weaknesses of the proposed methodology.

Index Terms—AC machines, vibration, transient, diagnosis

I. INTRODUCTION

Rotating electrical machinery represents a reliable and robust resource for electromechanical energy conversion. However, their failure and outage represent an economical burden and, in many occasions, a significant human life hazard. A high amount of rotating machines rely on rolling bearings to couple static and rotating machine parts. These are identified as critical constructive elements and the major cause of machine failure in low-voltage applications [1]. Thus, the early identification and diagnosis of bearing faults still attracts significant research attention.

The most widespread technique for bearing diagnosis is the monitoring of vibration signals [2]. Other techniques rely on phase current and stray flux measurement, which are also sensitive to localized bearing defects [3]. However, bearing fault signatures in current and stray flux are linked to the rotor eccentricity induced by radial displacement of the bearings [4]

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and thus, it represents an indirect way of signature acquisition. A wide number of techniques to diagnose bearings via vibration signals are found in literature, mainly during steady-state operation. Particularly, the analysis of the vibration envelope spectrum to detect localized bearing faults signatures is considered as a historically effective methodology [5]. Other methods for the steady-state evaluation rotating machine faults are based on the classic Fourier spectrum [6], empirical mode decomposition [7], or discrete wavelet decomposition [8].

The monitoring of vibration signals during varying speed conditions has been widely studied during last years [9]. Advanced signal processing methods can be classified between resampling and resampling-free techniques [10]. The first type, exploits the signal proportionality with respect the varying speed [11]. However, the speed signal should be measured or estimated. Methods that do not involve resampling are advantageous due to their ability to bypass dependencies on signal speed, distinguishing them from resampling approaches. Some resampling-free techniques to diagnose localized bearing faults are found in literature. In [12], the oscillatory behaviour-based signal decomposition is exploited to extract signatures of inner and outer race localized bearing faults. In [13] the authors pursue similar purposes also exploiting the signal demodulation.

The diagnosis of bearings during the electrical machine start-up is strongly linked to the varying-speed bearing diagnosis. Few resampling-free processing techniques to detect bearing faults during the machine start-up currently exist in literature. In [14], the authors compare different processing techniques to detect several machine faults during the directly-fed machine start-up. Specifically, an analysis is conducted on a defect in the outer race bearing, although the theoretical signature of the fault is not distinctly discerned. The analysis of the different localized fault signatures during an inverter-fed rotating machine start-up is presented in [15]. The work introduces a technique based on the time-frequency analysis

of the vibration envelope to identify ball element, inner, and outer race faults. The Short Time Fourier Transform (STFT) is utilized in this work, which presents obvious drawbacks related to the time-frequency resolution trade-off, among others. The MUSIC algorithm is identified in [14] as a promising tool to obtain increased frequency resolution and to better discern the qualitative evolutions of faults. The MUSIC algorithm is successfully applied to transient fault detection in works such as [16], [17].

The present manuscript aims at the qualitative identification of incipient bearing faults during the inverter-fed induction machine start-up. To this aim, the MUSIC algorithm is utilized to map the time-frequency evolutions of the vibration envelope spectrum. The method is implemented in the open-source HUST dataset, which contain vibration transient as well as the steady-state signals [18]. The manuscript is organized as follows. Section II describes the theoretical background behind bearing signatures, envelope spectrum and the MUSIC algorithm. Section III describes the experimental setup of the HUST dataset and identifies the characteristic frequencies depending on the different bearing geometries. Section IV presents the method results for different localized faults. Section V introduces a sensitivity analysis of the MUSIC algorithm parameters and performs a direct comparison with the linear STFT. Section VI summarizes the main findings and concludes the work.

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

A. Rolling element bearing localized fault signature

Rolling element bearings are composed of various elements, with paramount significance of the outer and inner races, rolling elements, and the cage. Localized faults or defects normally appear in the rolling elements, and on the races. Figure 1 (a) shows a disassembled version of a bearing while Figure 1 (b) describes the bearing main geometry characteristics. Localized faults produce a series equally spaced mechanical shocks in ideal conditions (i.e., without considering contact slip). The time spacing or frequency of these shocks is analytically defined depending on the bearing dimensions and the rotating speed. These expressions are given by [19]:

$$f_{BPFO} = \frac{n_b}{2} \left\{ 1 - \frac{d_b \cos(\theta)}{d_p} \right\} f_r \quad (1)$$

$$f_{BPFI} = \frac{n_b}{2} \left\{ 1 + \frac{d_b \cos(\theta)}{d_p} \right\} f_r \quad (2)$$

$$f_{CF} = \frac{1}{2} \left\{ 1 - \frac{d_b \cos(\theta)}{d_p} \right\} f_r \quad (3)$$

$$f_{BSF} = \frac{d_p}{2d_b} \left\{ 1 - \frac{d_b^2 \cos^2(\theta)}{d_p^2} \right\} f_r \quad (4)$$

where n_b represents the number of balls or rolling elements, d_b the ball diameter, d_p the ball pitch diameter and θ is the angle of load from the radial plane or ball contact angle. Equation 1 and 2 represent the ball-pass frequency of inner and outer races respectively (i.e., f_{BPFO} and f_{BPFI}), equation 3 represents

Fig. 1. (a) Spherical rolling element bearing disassembled, (b) Geometric description of the bearing

the cage frequency f_{CF} , and equation 4 the ball spin frequency f_{BSF} .

B. Envelope analysis and MUSIC algorithm

The analysis of the vibration envelope is a widespread technique to identify bearing defect signatures. To this aim, the Hilbert Transformation (*HT*) of the signal is exploited. The HT provides the same signal in complex notation, where the imaginary part is just an identical signal shifted 90 degree in phase. The signal envelope is obtained by computing the absolute value of the complex-valued signal.

The time-frequency representation of the vibration envelope signal is obtained by utilizing the MUSIC algorithm, which belongs to the subspace decomposition method category. These are mainly utilized to detect frequencies with low signal-to-noise ratio since it decomposes the space into signal and noise subspaces. The algorithm assumes a discrete signal (i.e., $x[n]$ $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N - 1$) that can be represented by a sum of p complex sinusoids plus a noise component $e[n]$ with zero mean and variance σ^2 . The decomposition of a signal $x(t)$ is thus described by [20]:

$$x(t) = \sum_{i=1}^p A_i e^{2\pi f_i t j + \varphi_i} + e(t) \quad (5)$$

where A_i is the amplitude, f_i is the frequency, and φ_i is the phase of the p -order complex sinusoids, and $e(t)$ is the noise signal. The complex sinusoid phases φ_i are uncorrelated random variables uniformly distributed within the interval

$[-\pi, \pi]$. The eigenvector decomposition of the whole signal $x(t)$ is composed by two orthogonal subspaces, formed by the signal and the noise autocorrelation matrices \mathbf{R}_s and \mathbf{R}_n respectively. The signal autocorrelation matrix is then expressed by:

$$\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{R}_s + \mathbf{R}_n = \sum_{i=1}^m A_i^2 \mathbf{e}(f_i) \mathbf{e}^H(f_i) + \sigma^2 \mathbf{I} \quad (6)$$

where m represent the number of considered frequencies, the index H is the hermitian transpose, \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix and $\mathbf{e}^H(f_i)$ is the discrete signal vector given by:

$$\mathbf{e}^H(f_i) = [1 \quad e^{-2\pi f_i j} \quad \dots \quad e^{-2\pi f_i j(N-1)}] \quad (7)$$

If the orthogonality condition is considered for both subspaces, the MUSIC pseudo-spectrum for a given time window is described by:

$$P_{MUSIC}(f) = \frac{1}{\sum_{i=p+1}^N |\mathbf{e}^H(f) \mathbf{v}_i|^2} \quad (8)$$

where \mathbf{v}_i represents the noise eigenvectors. Equation (8) is maximum when the signal and noise subspace projections are zero for a certain f_i . Practically, the MUSIC pseudo-spectrum identifies significant frequencies from a signal with strong noise presence. For increased number of considered complex sinusoids the better the high peak identification of the algorithm. However, the computational cost depends on the number of considered p-factors and the length of the time-window.

III. HUST DATASET DESCRIPTION

The methodology is tested on the open source HUST dataset [18]. The vibration signals are acquired in radial direction by using a suitable accelerometer (i.e., PCB 325C33) located in a dedicated bearing module. The shaft containing the bearing under test is excited by an induction machine, while different resistive torques are imposed by a powder brake. Figure 2 shows the utilized test-bench for vibration signal acquisition. The faults are implemented by wire-cutting different constructive elements inducing a micro-crack of 2 mm. The dataset

Fig. 2. HUST dataset test bench, extracted from [18]

contains signals for five different bearings from the same manufacturer. The sampling frequency for both steady-state and transient signals is 51.2 kHz. Table III shows the different bearing geometric features and the estimated characteristic coefficients following equations (1-4). The fault characteristic coefficients contain the term multiplying the rotating frequency (f_r) considering $\theta = 0$.

TABLE I
BEARING DIMENSIONS FROM HUST DATASET [18]

Bearing type	n_b	d_{in} [mm]	d_{out} [mm]	d_b [mm]	d_p [mm]
6204	8	20	47	7.6	33.5
6205	9	25	52	7.8	38.5
6206	9	30	62	9	46
6207	9	35	72	11	53.5
6208	9	40	80	12	60

TABLE II
ESTIMATED FAULT CHARACTERISTIC COEFFICIENTS ASSUMING $\theta = 0$

Bearing type	BPFO	BPFI	BSF	CF
6204	3.09	4.91	2.09	0.39
6205	3.59	5.41	2.37	0.4
6206	3.62	5.38	2.46	0.4
6207	3.57	5.43	2.33	0.4
6208	3.6	5.4	2.41	0.4

IV. ANALYSIS OF LOCALIZED FAULTS

The present section is aimed to the detailed investigation of different localized bearing faults during no-load operation. Due to manuscript length restrictions only the higher signal-to-noise ratio signals are selected, which coincide with the bearings labelled as 6204 for inner race fault, and 6207 for the outer race and rolling element faults. Figure 3 shows the time-domain transient signals and the steady-state envelope spectrum for the bearings under test at no-load.

The envelope of the transient signals introduced in figure 3 is provided by the absolute value of the HT. The HT yields a vector in the complex domain with identical length to the original signal. The imaginary component of this vector represents the original signal phase-shifted by 90 degrees. The envelope signal is then high-pass filtered to eliminate the DC component and down-sampled to avoid extremely high computational times. The filtered signal is input to the MUSIC algorithm to obtain the pseudo-spectrogram for each defined time-window. Figure 4 shows the obtained pseudo-spectrograms for the signals under study. These figures are obtained by setting the number of complex sinusoids p to 70 with a time window of 0.35 seconds and 95 % of window overlap. The rotational speed at no-load steady-state is 24.83 Hz.

The qualitative evolutions of the main fault components (i.e., f_{BPFO} , f_{BPFI} , and f_{BSF}) are clearly identified with adequate frequency resolution. Figure 4 (b) shows the rotating frequency modulations between f_r and f_{BPFI} . Note that for the no-load point, the modulations $f_{BPFI} - kf_r$; $k =$

Fig. 3. Localized fault transient signals and steady-state envelope spectrum analysis. No-load cases. (a) Bearing 6207 outer race fault, (b) Bearing 6204 inner race fault, (c) Bearing 6207 rolling element fault.

$1, 2, \dots, n$ are extremely close to the multiples of the rotating frequency f_r and thus, these are overlapped in the time-frequency map. The MUSIC algorithm does not clearly discriminate among extremely close harmonics in this case. Figure 4 (c) shows the cage frequency modulations around even multiples of f_{BSF} (i.e., $f_{BSF} \pm k f_{CF}$; $k = 1, 2, \dots, n$). These are clearly observed up to $k = 2$.

V. SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

The present section performs the sensitivity analysis of the time-frequency representation, elucidating the effects of the considered p complex sinusoids and different time-window characteristics. A signal with high modulation content is selected for the sensitivity analysis (i.e., rolling element fault defect with $f_{BSF} \pm k f_{CF}$ components). In this way, the effect of the different parameters on the time-frequency resolution, the elapsed computation time, and the qualitative identification of different trends can be assessed. In addition, the MUSIC time-frequency representation is compared with the STFT equivalent version.

Figure 5 shows the results from the performed sensitivity analysis for the signal under analysis (i.e., 6207 rolling element defect at no-load). The baseline parameters for the anal-

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 4. Localized fault transient analysis via MUSIC vibration envelope analysis. No-load cases. (a) Bearing 6207 outer race fault, (b) Bearing 6204 inner race fault, (c) Bearing 6207 rolling element fault.

ysis consists of 70 p -levels, a time window of 0.35 seconds, and 95 % overlap. The number of p complex sinusoids or p -levels strongly influences the identification of modulation com-

Fig. 5. Time-frequency representation parameter sensitivity analysis, 6207 rolling element fault zoom around $2f_{BSF}$ transition between transient and steady-state conditions, (a) p-level number, (b) overlap percentage, (c) time window length.

ponents as observed in figure 5 (a). However, the frequency resolution is not affected by the number of p-levels and thus, the sizes of the pseudo-spectrogram matrix are kept constant. The overlap levels clearly affect the discrimination between components mainly during the transient evolution. This can be easily observed in figure 5 (b). However, increased overlap levels increase the number of time windows needed to span the whole signal thus, increasing the matrix size in the x-axis. Figure 5 (c) elucidates the effect of the time window size. Increased time spans, directly decrease the time resolution and thus, the size of the pseudo-spectrogram x-axis. In the case of MUSIC representation, small time windows do not necessarily affect the frequency resolution as observed in the case of the linear STFT. However, small time windows may hinder the signal identification mostly for high number of p complex sinusoids. Table III shows the elapsed time for time-frequency map computation for different settings. The computation is

performed in a Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-1065G7, 1.50 GHz, 16 GB RAM, Matlab R2022b.

TABLE III
ELAPSED TIME FOR DIFFERENT TIME-FREQUENCY REPRESENTATION SETTINGS

p-levels	time [s]	overlap [%]	time [s]	window [s]	time [s]
20	1.25	95	2.889	0.55	2.87
70	3.21	80	1.2284	0.35	3.61
120	4.21	60	0.6123	0.15	5.13

Figure 6 shows the comparison between the STFT representation introduced in [15] and the proposed approach. The STFT representation shown in figure 6 is obtained by considering a time window of 0.4 s with 95% overlap and a hanning window for each time section. Both approaches accurately identify the qualitative trends of the main faulty component f_{BSF} and the modulations $f_{BSF} \pm kf_{CF}$. How-

Fig. 6. Comparison between vibration envelope time-frequency representations of the 6207 rolling element fault at no-load, (a) MUSIC, (b) STFT

ever, the MUSIC representation presents reduced distance between maximum and minimum values.

VI. CONCLUSION

The present paper introduces and thoroughly analyzes a methodology for the time-frequency representation of incipient localized bearing faults during an inverter-fed machine start-up. The technique is based on the representation of the vibration envelope spectrum via MUSIC pseudo-spectrogram. Different localized faults are analysed and a setting sensitivity analysis is performed including a comparison with a linear STFT. The analysis via MUSIC offers increased frequency resolution and overcomes the resolution trade-off of the STFT. The paper demonstrates the capabilities of the present technique to qualitatively discern fault evolutions that can be analytically estimated if the geometry of the bearing is known.

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